

The author <joeputhen@jesuits.net> serves the Word of God at Vidyajyoti Institute of Religious Studies, Delhi. Within the Christian Scripture, Luke-Acts is his area of specialization. As a Patna Jesuit, his religious formation has been initiated in Bihar.

Abstract: Stan Swamy (1937-2021) witnesses to Jesus through his prophetic ministry of conscientizing the Adivasis of Jharkhand. Through his commitment to redeeming “*jal, jangal, jameen*,” he “pours out” his life for the rights and dignity of the tribals of Chotanagpur, and thus upholds God’s kingdom.

Keywords: Stan Swamy, Prophet, Justice, Adivasis, God’s Kingdom, Bagaicha .

INTRODUCTION

This series, titled “GOSPEL in ACTION,” sheds light on Jesus’ witnesses who by their deeds culminating in the “pouring out of blood” (cf. Lk 22:20) testify to the good news of the risen Lord Jesus Christ.¹ Stan Swamy (1937-2021) witnesses to Jesus and proclaims God’s kingdom through his prophetic ministry that consists mostly of empowering the Adivasis of Jharkhand and helping them redeem their dignity. His committed engagement with the

¹ The twelve Jesus-witnesses introduced in the Series “GOSPEL in ACTION” in 2026 are: Devasahayam, Rani Maria, Kandhamal martyrs, Herman Rasschaert, Mathew Mannaparambil, Anthony Murmu, Stan Swamy, James Kottayil, Arul Doss, AT Thomas, Valsa John, and Tom Gafney. Each of these twelve proclaims the Gospel with a Spirit-guided praxis. The Acts of the Apostles and When the Gospel Grows Feet, a biography on Rutilio Grande, inspire the series-title “GOSPEL in ACTION.” In presenting each Jesus-witness, there is (1) a brief introduction to the martyr and their contextual Gospel praxis, and (2) a concise exposition to a defining characteristic of witnessing (martyria).

tribal society culminates in his martyrdom while being imprisoned under false charges.

1. A PROPHETIC LIFE “POURED OUT” WITH *ADIVASIS*

Stan Lourdusamy is born on 26 April 1937 at Viragalur, Tamil Nadu. His desire to become a Jesuit grows intense during his intermediate studies at St. Joseph’s, Tiruchirapalli. “As a compassionate and committed youth preparing to join the Jesuits from a alanded high-caste family in Tamil Nadu, Stan’s early growing took off amidst the social firmament of anti-caste, anti-untouchability movements with the growing influence of Periyar Ramaswamy Naickar.”² As a young Jesuit in the early 1970s, his social immersion among the Adivasis helps him understand tribal coexistence with nature, community living, sharing, and collective decision-making.

Two events during Stan’s stay in a Ho Adivasi village in Chaibasa shape his social perspective and prophetic commitment.³ According to him,

In one such village, I was staying at a student’s home. It was a mango season. One morning, we were sitting in their courtyard, under a mango tree laden with fruits. My student’s father pointed to a few branches of the tree and asked his son to bring down the ripe fruits. The boy did as he was told, and we enjoyed some of the fruits together. But my attention was drawn to one particular branch of the tree, which was still laden with ripe mangoes. The boy’s father had not asked him to pluck any fruit from that branch, and I thought that perhaps he had failed to notice it. So, I pointed to the branch and said, ‘There are plenty of ripe fruits on this branch. Why didn’t you ask your son to pick those too?’ He responded very simply,

² Cf. Antony Puthumattathil, “Becoming and Being Stan Swamy,” in *The Life and Legacy of Fr Stan Swamy, SJ (26 April 1937 – 5 July 2021): A Collective Remembrance* (Ranchi: Bagaicha, 2024), 27.

³ Stan Swamy recollects these two events during his interview with Tapan Bose. The Wire posted this conversation, taken place two years before his death, on YouTube posthumously. Cf. “An Interview with Fr Stan Swamy by Tapan Bose,” July 11, 2021, <https://youtu.be/bJyJENDcVE4> (accessed on 05.05.2026).

saying, ‘Those are fruits for the birds of the air. Nature has given freely, and so we share freely.’ This incident forced me to question my value system.⁴

The second event takes place during Stan’s visit to the village “Tuesday market.” He notices how an ordinary village woman is illtreated by the *baniyas* (local businesspersons). In sharp contrast to the value of sharing that the Adivasis uphold, the oppressors aim at grabbing even the little that the village tribals have and their greed undermine the dignity of the Adivasis. “As a Jesuit Priest Stan Swamy stormed into the fight against oppressive structures and forces that are at work especially in the marginal sections of India because he believed in a God who is a liberating God.”⁵ His advocacy and networking helps the Adivasis restore their rightful claim to land and other essential resources for a dignified living.

Stan shows a way forward for everyone committed to God’s kingdom. “We must be grateful to Stan for showing the way forward in the India of today, where democracy is crumbling and the powerful establishment is dealing with a heavy hand, anyone who does not submit quietly.”⁶

Stan’s legacy has ignited a renewal among the Adivasis and among those committed to egalitarian and just society. His model of conscientization is effective in promoting social justice and conservation of tribal values. His witness challenges all, especially Christians, to live their life prophetically, like Jesus.

2. PROPHET

In Jesus Christ, prophetic justice becomes incarnate justice. Stan is a prophet of justice in the tradition of Old

⁴ Cf. Stan Swamy, *I Am Not a Silent Spectator: Why Truth Has Become So Bitter, Dissent So Intolerable, Justice So Out of Reach* (Bangalore: Indian Social Institute, 2021), 8-9. Stan’s “autobiographical fragment, memory and reflection” contains many such events in his life.

⁵ Cf. Somy M. Mannoor, “The God of Stan Swamy,” *Ignis* 52/3 (2022): 55.

⁶ Cf. Frazer Mascarenhas, “Stan’s Spirituality: Identity, Comradeship, Communion,” *Ignis* 52/3 (2022): 8.

Testament prophets and as a continuation of Jesus' own prophetic ministry. His Spirit-empowered boldness aligns him with both Israel's prophetic tradition and Jesus', granting him visionary insight into God's heavenly purpose. His life and death, like Jesus', exemplify the prophetic call to confront injustice, reveal divine truth, and point to Christ—even at the cost of rejection. It confirms that his mission is rooted in the same Spirit-led prophetic witness that animated Israel's history and Jesus' ministry. Like Jesus' prophetic ministry, Stan's prophetic witness is bold, in continuity with the pattern of God-sent "prophet like Moses," and culminating in prophetic death.

Like the Prophets of the Old Testament, he reads the signs of the times, he assesses the situation, he stands for the rights of the marginalized, he engages in the political struggle of the masses, fearlessly speaks truth to the power, and ultimately pays the price. Stan Swamy shows us the way of collaboration, courage, commitment, and care. "In and through his incarceration and death, Stan Swamy emerged as an icon of resistance. No other Church personality in the recent past received such a great acclaim in the secular world as Stan did."⁷

CONCLUSION

Stan Swamy's life stands as a luminous witness to the Gospel enacted through courageous, restorative justice and prophecy. In his struggle for the dignity and liberation of the Adivasis, he embodies the prophetic ministry of Jesus, confronting oppressive systems while nurturing communities of equality. His life and sacrifice reveal that authentic discipleship demands costly love, yet it also unleashes transformative hope among the marginalized. Stan legacy summons Christians today to responsible social engagement that that results in the growth of God's kingdom.

⁷ Edwin Rodrigues SJ, "Editorial: Let's Keep the Legacy of Stan Swamy Burning Brightly," *VJTR* 86/7 (July 2022): 481-482.